

THE IMPACT OF TEACHERS' REFLECTIVE JOURNAL WRITING ON THEIR SELF-EFFICACY

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Abstract

Teacher efficacy has been proven to be an important variable in effective teaching. One challenge in teacher education is to provide strategies and processes which equip teachers to improve their self-efficacy. A strategy that has received considerable attention in the literature is reflective journal writing. The objective of this study was to explore the impact of reflective journal writing as a self-assessment technique on teachers' self-efficacy and also teachers' attitude toward such a practice. The participants were 40 Iranian female teachers in two experimental and control groups. The particular treatment used in the experimental group was reflective journal writing. At the beginning and the end of the semester, both groups completed a questionnaire regarding self-efficacy to investigate the possible effect of reflective journal writing on teachers' self-efficacy. Teachers' perceptions about reflective journal writing were also analyzed based on content analysis at the end of the semester. The results revealed that writing reflective journals had an impact on promoting the teachers' self-efficacy.

Keywords: journal writing, reflective journal writing, self-efficacy, teachers' self-efficacy

1. Introduction

During the past two decades, self-efficacy has emerged as a highly effective predictor of teachers' success and learning. The concept of teacher self-efficacy refers to the beliefs of teachers related to their capabilities to affect the learning outcomes of students including those with low motivation and low ability to learn (Bandura, 1977; Tschannen-Moran, Hoy, & Hoy, 1998). It can be argued that the levels of teachers' efforts, targets and desires differ depending on self-efficacy beliefs (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001). Teachers with high teacher self-efficacy make more efforts to overcome the problems they face, and they can maintain these efforts longer (Bandura, 1977; 1986). There are also differences between teachers with high and low self-efficacy beliefs in issues such as using new techniques and giving feedback to students with learning disabilities (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001). Teacher efficacy stems from lifelong experiences resulting in teacher beliefs and perceptions affecting how teachers

see themselves individually and collectively. However, few teachers, especially novice teachers, question their beliefs and perceptions; most teachers tend to view their beliefs or perceptions as the commonly assumed and shared ways of believing and acting. Therefore, few teachers enjoy a high sense of self-efficacy beliefs. In order to enhance teachers' self-efficacy in their practice, evaluation systems that identify teachers' strengths and weaknesses for improvement are needed. Researchers have proposed various ways to evaluate teacher self-efficacy and improvement among which teacher self-assessment has been paid less attention.

Teacher self-assessment is an important source of self-efficacy information in which teachers observe their effect on student achievement, make a judgment about how well they attained their instructional goals, and reflect on how satisfied they are (Ross & Bruce, 2007). Confronting the concept of self-assessment, most of the research has been devoted to students' self-assessment in regard to educational achievement. Moreover, studies concerning teacher evaluation have mostly focused on teacher evaluation by a supervisor or an observer. Reflective journal writing as a self-assessment strategy of reflection and decision making is today established as a key concept in recent discussions of teachers' learning (Farrell, 2008). Reflective practice is seen as a teaching technique which involves constant questions about one's own teaching and then attempting to take a more systematic approach to practices and to work with others who had such common interests and questions as yours (Pickett, 1999 cited in Maarof, 2007). The benefits of reflective writing are stated in several studies. Studies have shown the role of reflective writing in promoting reflection amongst pre-service and in-service teachers (Charles, 1997). Hiemstra (2001) pointed out a number of potential benefits of keeping reflective journals, such as increased ability of self-expression, self-discovery and reduced stress. Reflective writing can be used by teachers in order to reflect on their teaching attitudes and practices. Although some research has examined the academic and cognitive value of reflective practice, little has sought the psychological impact of reflective writing on the personal development of teachers. Therefore, the present research has attempted to develop an understanding of the concept of teacher reflective journal writing and its possible impact on teacher self-efficacy.

2. Review of Literature

Teacher Self-efficacy

Teacher efficacy concept is originated from Albert Bandura's social cognitive theory (1997). The mentioned theory has influenced educational organizations, which has been studied by researchers who use a sociocognitive approach to understand how the emergent theories of individuals impact organizational performance (Bandura, 1997). The beliefs teachers hold in relation to their own effectiveness are known as teacher efficacy. Teacher efficacy influences Teachers' instructional decisions, which ultimately shape students' educational experiences, and in turn affect academic development outcomes (Romi & Leyser, 2006). Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk-Hoy (2001) referred to teacher efficacy as a teacher's "judgment of his or her capabilities to bring about desired outcomes of students' engagement and learning, even among those students who may be difficult or unmotivated" (p. 783). There are two dimensions

concerning teacher efficacy including "general teacher efficacy" which refers to teachers' harbor beliefs about their own personal abilities to influence their students' learning and achievements and "personal teaching efficacy" which is beliefs concerning the extent to which teaching can overcome external influences on the student. (Ashton & Webb, 1986). These two dimensions (personal teacher efficacy and general teacher efficacy) can be related to pre-service and in-service teachers' beliefs about control, management, and motivation (Woodcock, 2011). Research in connection with teacher self-efficacy beliefs shows that high self-efficacy teachers are more likely to persevere in their attempts to achieve learning goals when they encounter obstacles, tend to experiment with effective instructional strategies, and are more willing to run risks in their classrooms (Bruce, Esmonde, Ross, Dookie & Beatty, 2010). Many studies are in favor of positive influences of efficacy beliefs on abilities regarding teachers' efficient classroom management and interaction with students. It has been found that teachers' cultural and social backgrounds also seem to affect teachers' sense of self efficacy (Lina & Gorrellb, 2001). Gender and years of experience as other factors have been explored to affect teachers' efficacy beliefs, too. Several studies have examined the effects of teacher education concerning teachers' sense of efficacy. In summary, teacher efficacy is linked to academic achievement and teacher behaviors are known to affect academic achievement. Therefore, teacher's sense of efficacy as an important variable in research on teaching deserves the continued attention of investigators in this area of inquiry.

Teacher Reflective Journal Writing

Reflective writing in teacher education is a developmental process, performed before and after teaching episodes. Writing journals as a learning tool is mediating between existing and new knowledge. Kerka (2002) referred to the power of journal writing as "breaking habitual ways of thinking, enhancing the development of meta-cognition, increase awareness of tacit knowledge, facilitate self-exploration and work out solutions to problems". There are many reasons for teachers to develop reflective practice. Perhaps the most important is that teachers need to be reflective in order to deal with the inevitable uncertainties involved in everyday decisions that affect the progress of students. According to Larrivee & Cooper (2001), effective teachers should engage in both critical inquiry and thoughtful reflection, encountering all the complexities, ambiguities, and dilemmas that characterize today's classrooms. Teaching is a complex endeavor that necessitates continuous learning as well as the capacity to be reflective. Many look upon the development of reflective practice as the foundation for the highest professional competence (Larrivee & Cooper, 2001). One of the major goals of reflective writing is achieving higher levels of reflective thinking. Clark (1994) believed that initiating dialogues based on questions may result in different and higher levels of thinking. Davis (2003, 2006) encouraged teachers to use integrative reflective practice, reflect on multiple aspects of teaching, hoping to improve through these practices. She suggested that teachers need support and practice in reflective writing otherwise they write "unproductive reflections", which are solely descriptive, without much analysis: a list of ideas rather than connecting them logically (Davis, 2006). The discussion above indicates that reflective writing in teacher education is viewed as a tool for better teaching, without examining a direct

link between them. Reflection in teacher's professional development is seen as an instrument for change, involvement in research, and self-assessment (Avalos, 2011).

3. Research Questions and Hypotheses

Research questions guiding the process of the study were:

1. Does teachers' reflective journal writing improve their self-efficacy?
2. What are teachers' attitudes toward reflective journal writing?

Based on the first research question, the following null hypothesis was proposed.

Teachers' reflective journal writing does not improve their self-efficacy.

4. Methodology

Participants

The participants of this study were 40 Iranian female EFL teachers working in Iran Language Institute (ILI) in Kermanshah. The participants' years of teaching experience ranged from 5 to 9 years. There were two groups of teachers, 20 in the experimental group, and 20 in the control group. The teachers in the experimental group received reflective journal writing training.

Instruments

The instruments used in this study included journal entries written by teachers every week used as the treatment in the experimental group, a teacher self-efficacy questionnaire served as pre and post-tests, as well as paragraphs written by teachers including teachers' attitudes and ideas about reflective journal writing practice. Reflective journal writing process was on the basis of Burton (2009) framework. The present framework was used as it encouraged integrative reflections, reflecting on multiple aspects of teaching, hoping to develop through these practices a more complex view of teaching. Therefore, it included different types of reflective writing (descriptive writing, descriptive reflection, dialogic reflection, and critical reflection) identified by Hatton and Smith (1995). This framework of reflective writing is presented as a series of simple-to-follow steps addressed to a teacher who has not previously written reflectively. The steps involve writing responses to a short series of essential questions. They are "What happened?", "How did it happen?", "Why did it happen?" and "What does it mean?". The reflective writing process begins with a description of, for example, an incident, a phenomenon observed, or an unresolved teaching puzzle by choosing a simple incident or concern (e.g., use of a teaching aid in a specific lesson). The second step of reflection begins to deepen. Writing in response to a "how" question enables teachers to comment on what they wrote before, to revise or elaborate it. The third step includes a response to a "why"-type question. As teachers write on the cause, effect, and meaning of their incident, topic or problem, they can find that they are beginning to theorize and relate their writing to other events or reading resources. Reflective writing process continues in response to questions such as "What does this mean to me now?". On each occasion, teachers give themselves further opportunities to deepen and broaden their reflections and link them, for example, to reflections on other experiences. By following the process

explained above, teachers can write systematically and flesh out their writing. Being systematic and contextualizing what they write, enables them to explain their reflections later on, so that they have lasting credibility and continuing potential for further learning (Burton, 2009). Teacher's self-efficacy was measured using Bandura's self-efficacy questionnaire (1997). This questionnaire was used as it reflected on the meaning of teacher self-efficacy based on social cognitive theory. Bandura (1997) pointed out that teachers' sense of efficacy is not necessarily uniform across the many different types of tasks teachers are asked to perform, nor across different subject matter. In response, he constructed a 30-item instrument with seven subscales: efficacy to influence decision making, efficacy to influence school resources, instructional efficacy, disciplinary efficacy, efficacy to enlist parental involvement, efficacy to enlist community involvement, and efficacy to create a positive school climate. Each item is measured on a 9-point scale anchored with the notations: "nothing, very little, some influence, quite a bit, a great deal". This measure attempted to provide a multifaceted picture of teachers' efficacy beliefs without becoming too narrow or specific. The reliability of the present instrument was tested through Cronbach's Alpha which was found to be 0.91. The validity was supported by findings of prior research (Zimmerman & Bandura, 1994).

Procedure

In order to answer the main research questions, at the beginning of the semester, both experimental and control groups were chosen from teachers working in Iran Language Institute. The purpose of the study was explained to the participants before following the procedure. The selected participants were randomly assigned to control and experimental groups. Bandura's self-efficacy questionnaire was distributed among both experimental and control groups as the pre-test of the present study. Participants were asked to complete the questionnaire. The experimental group was informed of the purpose of writing a journal which was deliberately to "think about action with a view to its improvement" (Hatton and Smith, 1995, p. 8), self-awareness, improvement of critical thinking, and self-improvement. The procedure of the study was explained to the participants. A five-page pamphlet including guidelines in the process of writing a journal was given to the participants. The pamphlet provided teachers with what the concept of journal writing was and included four steps for teachers to follow in the process of writing a journal based on Burton (2009) framework. The teachers in the experimental group were required to keep journal entries every week, which included the reflections of the teachers on their teaching experiences and performance in class and their experiences in the institute they were teaching as a whole. The duration of the teaching practice was 10 weeks. Journal entries were collected by the instructor (researcher) every week. Journal entries were checked by the instructor in order to make sure the participants were following the steps they had to consider in the process of journal writing. Factors such as length, grammar or spelling of the entries were not of the main concerns. If a participant had failed to follow the suggested format in the process of reflective writing, the instructor would have given the required advice to the participant. After ten week reflective writing practice by the participants in the experimental group, they were asked to write down their ideas and

opinion on journal writing to elicit information on teachers' conception of reflection and of reflective journals. Finally, both experimental and control groups were invited to mark the self-efficacy questionnaire once more as the post-test of the study. The scores of the pre and post-self-efficacy questionnaires were analyzed based on the following procedure.

5. Data Analysis and Results

To find out the impact of reflective journal writing on self-efficacy, both qualitative and quantitative data collection procedures were followed. Quantitative data was drawn from Bandura's self-efficacy questionnaire which served as the pre and post-test of the study. The qualitative data was drawn from the analysis of teachers' ideas toward reflective journal writing in their final journal entries at the end of the treatment. The scores on the questionnaire were analyzed through t-test. Within both experimental and control groups, an independent t- test was conducted to check the probable effect of reflective journal writing on promoting teachers' self-efficacy. For the control and the experimental groups, the mean scores were analyzed to see if there was any significant difference between the mean scores of the self-efficacy questionnaire on the pretest. Similarly, the mean scores for the experimental and the control groups were analyzed to find out if there was any difference between two sets of scores on the post-tests. Teachers' attitudes about journal writing were analyzed based on content analysis to investigate the effect of reflective journal writing treatment on teachers in the experimental group. Figure 1 depicts the mean difference of the pre-test.

Table 1 displays the independent sample t-test for the pre-test in the experimental and control groups. As indicated, the observed significance is larger than the alpha decision level set, therefore it can be concluded that there is no significant difference between the groups at the beginning of the study.

Table 1
Independent Sample t-test for the Pre-test

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Ex Gr	20	152.1	13.69	-.373	38	.711
Co Gr	20	154	18.19			

In Table 1, it is indicated that there is not a significant difference between the control and the experimental pre-test scores [$t(38) = -.373; p = .711 > 0.05$]. Table 2 indicates the independent sample t-test for the post-test in the experimental and the control groups.

Table 2
Independent Sample t-test for the Post-test

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Ex Gr	20	175.1	15.99	3.452	38	.001
Co Gr	20	156	18.71			

As table 2 indicates, there is a significant difference between the control and experimental post-test scores [$t(38) = 3.452$; $p < 0.05$]. As the significance equals .001 and it is less than .05, it can be concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the experimental group ($M = 175.1$) self-efficacy was higher than that of the control group ($M = 156$) at the end of the treatment. Based on the results in Figures 1, 2, and Tables 1, and 2, we can realize that reflective journal writing as a self-assessment technique was effective in enhancing teacher's self-efficacy.

Teachers' Perceptions toward Reflective Journal Writing

Apart from the results of the self-efficacy questionnaire, analyzing the teachers' ideas about journal writing through paragraphs they wrote at the end of the treatment showed that they had gained more confidence in their teaching. The 20 teachers in the experimental group were requested to write on their thoughts of reflective journal writing at the end of the treatment. In general, the teachers provided a positive response to reflective journal writing. An overwhelming majority (90%) of the teachers stated that they enjoyed the experience of writing a journal. A common response was that reflecting in writing assisted them in evaluating their teaching, in terms of their strengths and weaknesses in conducting lessons in class. Only 10 percent of the teachers (two of the participants) said that they did not like journal writing. The reasons included lacking enough time to write a journal and considering writing as a boring process. A majority admitted that writing a reflective journal helped them in their teaching and learning process and that it assisted them in identifying mistakes or weaknesses in their teaching. In their paragraphs some of the teachers wrote:

T1: *I am thinking of myself if reflective journal writing improved my teaching or not. I think yes. When I look at my writing paper which we wrote every week, I can see my progress specially in dealing with class management aspects.*

T2: *In journal writing, I had to reflect on what I had learned as a teacher at the end of the week. Writing a journal enabled me to rethink what I had heard and had done after the lesson. I got familiar with the word reflection in the whole process... Now I am not just finding reasons, but also reflecting on different solutions ... I have learned a lot through reflection, and now I can apply the knowledge in the future."*

T3: *I think that this experience was very important for me because this was the first time that I was assessing my own teaching process. This way, I could accept my teaching weaknesses and strengths more easily as I had found them out by myself. Through reflection, I tried to pay more attention to the problems I had already ignored and sought for useful solutions to them.*

T4: *I think reflective journal writing was great as it helped me to deal with a problem I had in one of my classes. I had difficulties in making some of my students understand their homework assignment in English at the beginning of the term. I had to go back and teach again the concepts that I had taught before and explain the assignment again. Through reflective writing, I found that I could write their homework assignment on the board in order to avoid any confusion.*

Based on teachers' perceptions on their journal writing practice in their paragraphs, it can be concluded that most of the teachers found reflective journal writing to be beneficial to teacher development.

6. Discussion and Conclusion

Since the introduction of the concept of self-efficacy in social sciences, research in different areas of education has investigated the contributions of teacher efficacy perceptions to various instructional variables and has shown, on most of the occasions, that there is a significant positive correlation between teacher self-efficacy and these variables. In this study, the researcher aimed to promote self-efficacy of the participants through using reflective journal writing as a self assessment technique and by giving them active roles to assess their own performance with an expectation of an increase in their self-efficacy. Similarly, in a study conducted by Ross & Bruce (2007), the aim was to increase teacher efficacy of mathematic teachers through a professional development program. They found that there was a positive effect, although the results were statistically significant only for teacher confidence in managing students. In another study conducted by Bruce et al. (2010), the effects of sustained classroom-embedded teacher professional learning on teacher efficacy and related student achievement was analyzed. The results revealed that there was an indirect but powerful relationship between increasing teacher efficacy and increasing student achievement. Here, the present study examined the impact of teachers' reflective journal writing on their self-efficacy. On the basis of the results of the statistical analysis of the self-efficacy questionnaire, and teachers' positive ideas toward reflective journal writing in their final paragraphs, it can be concluded that involvement of teachers in reflective writing practice enhanced the self-efficacy of the teachers.

Limitations

The present study is limited to a specific community of Iranian EFL experienced teachers in Iran Language Institute. Therefore, the results do not represent all the EFL teachers (including both experienced and inexperienced teachers). Another limitation of the study is its being dependent on the honesty and sincerity of the English language teachers who participated in the study. Finally, the sample size of this study was small. Despite the transparency of the study findings, a larger number of the participants would have permitted a greater reliance to the results.

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